

Evaluating the impacts of CHARTER science-policy dialogue

Deliverable 7.15

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 54 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Author(s): Sirpa Rasmus and Mia Landauer (LAY) and others in CHARTER coordination team

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Draft	
Final	x

Type		
R	Document, report	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	
OTHER		

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission services)	

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13.1.25	Sirpa Rasmus, Mia Landauer	1 st draft version
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Introduction

Many of CHARTER WP6 and WP7 deliverables have been targeted to maximize our impact and to assure that the dissemination and exploitation goals are met:

- D7.7 and D7.20: Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR), and its update
- D7.8: The Stakeholder Analysis Template is designed and used to identify the groups, their potential influence on generating impact and interest in our research.
- D7.9: Planning and designing an introductory poster
- D7.10: establishing the Expert Advisory Group.
- D7.11-D7.13, D7.17: Annual reports and meetings of the Consortium, Steering Committee and the Expert Advisory Group
- D6.2: Mapping of stakeholder network required for the co-design of pathway narratives by means of a social network analysis
- D6.4: Co-design of policy options to inform climate adaptation and mitigation policies and practices and enhance the viability and resilience of Arctic local livelihoods.
- D6.5: Cross-cutting work to develop Arctic strategy and provide policy recommendations.
- D7.16: List of created scientific publications

This report on CHARTER science-policy dialogue complements the work presented in reports listed above. The original aim of this part of the work was to evaluate the impacts of the project based on qualitative interviews with policy- and decision-makers in the region, about their knowledge of CHARTER research themes, and to link this with a social network mapping and social network analysis, carried out in CHARTER (Landauer et al. 2021; Eronen et al. 2023). The idea was to trace how findings are communicated from person to person until they reach the policy or not.

In practice this proved out to be a very difficult task. The actual impact (seen in the decision-making, or in practices and planning related to northern livelihoods) is hard or even impossible to trace during a project. Also the work on social network analysis has been slower than expected, meaning that combining the findings would have been based on early, and rather limited results. In view of impact, we felt that asking about CHARTER research themes was slightly lacking ambition, and also the link between that knowledge (knowledge on climate change, knowledge on biodiversity change, for example) and the impact of our science-policy dialogue is vague. And we faced practical difficulties to reach correct people, with time to participate in interviews, at this stage of the project. Because of these reasons, WP7 and WP6 researchers decided to create a questionnaire survey and distribute this to relevant actors who had participated in CHARTER events and co-production of knowledge. We especially aimed at decision

makers, but with a wide definition – we naturally considered people working in policymaking, decision-making and administration in ministries or at EU, regional and municipality level, also in Sápmi (Sámi parliament, Sámi Council), but also people closely involved in northern land-use development, and people representing interest groups of livelihoods, nature conservation, and so on. In the questionnaire we asked about CHARTER research themes, but also about experiences on participating in CHARTER work, and views related to research needs listed by CHARTER, and policy recommendations given.

Taking this approach, we aimed at material that is useful also when planning for future projects, especially their participatory work and outreach.

Material and methods

We used the Webropol -tool to build the survey, as well as to collect the responses. The appearance of the survey is shown in Figure 1. Survey questions are listed in box 1.

https://link.webpolsurveys.com/Participation/Public/76b5f166-c58a-4637-a3c7-7f464d97d861?displayId=... Search

https://link.webpolsurveys.com/Participation/Public/76b5f166-c58a-4637-a3c7-7f464d97d861?displayId=Fin3223194&surveyLocale=en

CHARTER SCIENCE-POLICY DIALOGUE

2. Please estimate to what degree you got new information, or gained knowledge and insights about CHARTER main themes, because of CHARTER work (1 = not at all; 5 = plenty):

	1	2	3	4	5
Climate change in Northern regions (snow and ice covers, weather events...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Changing biodiversity in Northern regions (vegetation, food-webs...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interactions of environmental changes and socio-economic developments in local communities and traditional livelihoods (for example adaptation needs and actions)	<input type="radio"/>				
Local knowledge, local future views	<input type="radio"/>				
Land use and land management in the Northern area (incl. reindeer management)	<input type="radio"/>				
Policy options and recommendations (related to decision-making in climate, biodiversity and land-use related matters, incl. local participation)	<input type="radio"/>				

Please give one finding or insight that you consider as especially useful:

Figure 1. Appearance of the “CHARTER science-policy dialogue” Webropol survey

In the cover letter we shortly gave basic information about CHARTER, together with a link to project webpage, and main aim of CHARTER: to advance the adaptive capacity of Arctic communities to climatic and biodiversity changes. It was also mentioned, that to achieve this goal, expertise from various disciplines has been combined with a strong participatory approach, and that person asked to participate had been involved in CHARTER work through interviews, workshops, conference sessions, or other ways of participation. It was mentioned that answers of the survey were used to assess the quality of potential impact of CHARTER, participation was voluntary, none of the 12 questions was mandatory, and the survey was anonymous. In the beginning of the survey it was nevertheless possible to include information about respondent's institutional affiliation, and tell shortly about their role/work. It was also possible to tell how they had participated in CHARTER activities.

The survey was open for a month (mid-Dec 2024 – mid-Jan 2025). The Finnish version was sent to approximately 80 individuals, known to have attended CHARTER policy events (Helsinki, Rovaniemi, online), workshops in northern Finland (Savukoski, Ylläs, Rovaniemi, Inari, online), or CHARTER final meeting (Rovaniemi). Some had attended seminars about regional development, or seminars or educational events organized with science journalists and Sámi parliament in Finland, with CHARTER material presented. Some had been part of a working group aiming at development of national governance related to reindeer husbandry, or working group aiming at climate change adaptation, with CHARTER researchers and CHARTER material involved in the work. In addition, The English version was sent to approximately 20 individuals, known to have attended CHARTER policy events (Brussels, Copenhagen) and workshops organized together with projects Arctic Hubs and JUSTNORTH (Nordic countries), or CHARTER annual meetings (Rovaniemi, Tromsø). The list of receivers included several names/actors listed already in CHARTER stakeholder mapping (D7.8, list further developed when working towards D6.2, about social network analysis).

Box 1: Content of the D7.15 survey (“CHARTER science-policy dialogue”)

1. Did you feel involved, and that your knowledge was appreciated, when you participated in CHARTER work? What we could do better in the future, so that meaningful involvement, balanced co-production of knowledge and inclusion of different knowledge systems are ensured?

2. Please estimate to what degree you got new information, or gained knowledge and insights about CHARTER main themes, because of CHARTER work:

- Climate change in Northern regions (snow and ice covers, weather events...)
- Changing biodiversity in Northern regions (vegetation, food-webs...)
- Interactions of environmental changes and socio-economic developments in local communities and traditional livelihoods (for example adaptation needs and actions)
- Local knowledge, local future views
- Land use and land management in the Northern area (incl. reindeer management)
- Policy options and recommendations (related to decision-making in climate, biodiversity and land-use related matters, incl. local participation)

Please give one finding or insight that you consider as especially useful:

To whom have you or might you communicate new knowledge or insights that you have gained over the project lifespan?

Do you think this information has been or will be used in planning processes, decision-making, outreach, or in some other way? How?

3. CHARTER has had two cross-cutting themes: “Tools and data for Arctic Strategies”, and “Public dialogue on the Arctic”.

- To your knowledge, has CHARTER been able to produce useful data, in a useful form, and useful tools to support future research and decision-making?
- In your opinion, has CHARTER been able to actively participate in public dialogue on the Arctic, and/or foster a dialogue in new, meaningful ways?

4. CHARTER has given some policy recommendations. To what degree you agree on their importance?

- Understanding Arctic landscapes as cultural landscapes, not as wilderness
- Respecting multiple knowledge systems and integrating local and Indigenous viewpoints in land management and land-use planning
- Building adaptive capacity of local communities to cope with climate change and other pressures.
- Strengthening local possibilities to act in diverse futures, by supporting learning, education, preparedness, increased resources
- Nexus approach in policy and governance to enable decision-making considering biodiversity, climate change, land use and local communities & livelihoods together
- Developing and managing multi-use landscapes
- Holistic coordination of land-use to avoid cumulative impacts on environment and local livelihoods.
- Developing the assessment of cumulative land-use impacts

5. CHARTER has listed some critical knowledge gaps and research needs. To what degree you agree?

- Research on land use changes and socio-ecological systems
- Co-creation of cross-disciplinary knowledge with local and Indigenous communities
- Monitoring non-native species and novel ecosystems
- Research on challenges and opportunities posed by the emergence of novel ecosystems for local and Indigenous communities
- Integrating local views and needs into climate model development
- Complementing field efforts with satellite interpretation tools and drone campaigns
- Research on reindeer pasture management activities vs lichen recovery

What other urgent research needs there are, in your opinion?

Results

The survey yielded only small number of responses (n=10, see the appendix for details). Even though disappointing, this was not a surprise - 10% response rate is typical for questionnaire surveys. From CHARTER perspective, this small number of respondents seemed to represent key actors, anyhow. Most of the respondents had good understanding on CHARTER work, and were well informed, thinking about assessing our work and its potential impact. Two participants did not indicate the way how they had participated the project, and also felt low degree of involvement and inclusion.

Survey respondents had generally felt involved (and their knowledge appreciated) when participating in CHARTER work. The project had had a positive and respectful undertone, and the respondents felt that the cooperation intensified towards the end.

What we could do better in the future, to ensure meaningful involvement, balanced co-production of knowledge and inclusion of different knowledge systems? Respondents gave some suggestions:

- Using research methods that are locally acceptable and not too laborious
- Supporting more cross-border dialogue (between herders)
- Inclusion of people not attending workshops, possessing “silent knowledge”.
- Researchers should involve themselves in everyday work to observe dynamics and interview on-site people who remain in the background.
- More stakeholder events, especially physical but even online, would be appreciated.
- It would be beneficial for Sámi reindeer herders of Norway, Sweden, and Finland to have joint conversations.
- The busy times of the reindeer herding year should be avoided, and compensation should be paid for time spent in project work.
- Choosing carefully the right data collection methods as they can affect the material obtained and their interpretation.

New information, knowledge and insights were gained on all CHARTER main themes (Figure 2a). Based on open answers, especially useful insights were got on changing summer conditions and different narratives related to reindeer grazing impacts in different Nordic countries. Workshops were seen as “well-planned and well-facilitated”, but link between knowledge and action and more physical encounters were asked for.

To whom respondents might communicate new knowledge or insights? These were for example mentioned: local development work, municipality, management of reindeer husbandry, general public. What about usefulness of the information in planning processes, decision-making, outreach? This remains as a question mark, but respondents mentioned local development projects and promoting interests of local livelihoods. The information has been used in planning processes, decision-making, outreach, and local development and as part of stakeholders’ own work. It is considered useful for policymaking at local, national, and EU levels. However, it has not been used in advocacy work yet, and it is uncertain how well information works as a background

material. By following how other (researchers) succeed in integrating Indigenous knowledge into research data is recommended.

Factors limiting the use of information: not enough understanding on impacts of certain actions; not being able to apply knowledge; irrelevant information to certain stakeholder groups. One challenge that was mentioned is the massive amount of everyday information from which it is increasingly difficult to filter out the most important things. Geopolitical tensions. Money and bureaucracy. Negative attitude against reindeer herding. Old attitudes and tensional aims related to northern land-use.

Respondents thought that CHARTER topics are interesting, the project has been able to produce useful data, in a useful form, and by means of useful tools. Also, CHARTER had been able to participate in, and keep up public dialogue on the Arctic, and/or foster a dialogue in new, meaningful ways. Nevertheless, one respondent reminded that more dialogue between researchers and others is needed - and continuation after the project, as well. But already as such it was considered helpful by one respondent to better consider issues concerning the Sámi and Sapmi at the national level. Concrete actions are challenging, but workshops and simulations are helpful. However, more participation is needed, particularly in non-researcher-to-researcher and internal discussions. The detailed results should be communicated, in particular directly to stakeholders.

a)

Figure 2. New information gained (a), agreeing on policy recommendations (b) and research needs (c) (1 = not at all / not important at all; 5 = plenty / strongly agree). More details in the appendix.

Respondents generally agreed with most of our **policy recommendations** (Fig. 2b); most often with “Nexus approach in policy and governance to enable decision-making considering biodiversity, climate change, land use and local communities & livelihoods together”. Same implies to **knowledge gaps and research needs** (Fig. 2c). These were seen as the most important ones: “Research on land use changes and socio-ecological systems” and “Co-creation of cross-disciplinary knowledge with local and Indigenous communities”.

Respondents also listed some other **urgent research needs**: changing socioeconomic landscapes in remote, rural communities, adaptation of reindeer herding to changing summer conditions, impacts of dry summers on lichen pastures. How to utilize reindeer grazing as part of the nature management, and as an adaptation action – acknowledging also varying herding practices and cultures between and within districts? Climate change and natural diversity reduction are evident in daily life, and measures are needed to address these issues. The impact of changing climate and environmental conditions on the ecosystem and thereby on livelihoods and people’s everyday lives. Impacts, for example, on the interactions between different animal species (predator-prey relationships). The missing link between knowledge and action was mentioned again – mitigating the climate change, and adaptation actions, are needed even if these are “bad for the economy”!

Discussion – linking this to other CHARTER work

The conclusions (linking findings to other CHARTER work) are very preliminary, but still provide some basis for the future work.

This kind of survey can clearly be used to assess the quality of the potential impact – and information like this is valuable to researchers, when planning future projects and their policy connections, outreach, and knowledge co-production (especially when adding to other analyses, like our work on social influence; and our work on nexus approach in Arctic policy-making (Landauer et al. 2021; Eronen et al. 2023; Rasmus et al. 2024).

Both scientific work, and outreach in research projects, can serve increasing the awareness and understanding, and taking action, and exploiting research results. Awareness may be increased and understanding gained within scientific community, but also within local communities and several stakeholder groups. Action can be taken and exploitation of results can happen by fellow-researchers, and also by for example EU-level research funding agencies and in regional land-use planning, local decision making, and so on. We expect that CHARTER will have long-lasting and significant impact through our publications, data, and research tools developed (<https://zenodo.org/communities/charter/>).

We have also learnt lessons that will serve future projects aiming at interaction and knowledge co-production with local communities and Indigenous societies (Doering et al. 2022 being an important contribution, to this end).

CHARTER held the co-production of knowledge as a central principle of the project design and involved local people in all stages of the research. Throughout the project our research partners have been involved through focus group discussion where our preliminary results have been discussed, through workshops where knowledge has been co-produced, or as important partners in fieldwork. This approach has allowed us to make sure our research has local relevance and impact – and that we are first to hear the emerging research topics from local practitioners. What we have learnt is that this work should not finish when CHARTER finishes – continuation is the key for our local collaborations. We also acknowledge that in-person contacts and encounters are significant – and often unplanned, even random. The importance of these was worded nicely by one survey respondent:

“I don’t suggest fixing any specific thing, but I emphasize the importance of in-person, physical encounters (in meetings, seminars, workshops). Considering the thought of others is like correcting the compass course during a long hike. First your own thoughts go approximately to certain direction, but the more knowledge you get from others, the better you can target your own thoughts and conclusions. This does not happen without meetings with other people. And Teams and Zoom meetings are like poor-quality compasses with a needle that swings here and there. Physical meeting is like a high-quality compass with modest needle movement; this makes correction of the direction more precise.”

Policy briefs, background papers and events explaining these, scientific papers relevant for decision making, outreach and communication, and direct interaction with people making decisions can all have an impact. These have been the means CHARTER has used to participate in public dialogue on Arctic. This impact is hard or even impossible to trace during a project. There may be regional, national or EU-level developments where CHARTER work and results will contribute to, but this is an issue for future assessments. Nevertheless, we see a great value in the work we have been carrying out, aims being to increase understanding on northern everyday life and strengthen the knowledge base of decision-makers, to act as a link between local level and national/EU-level, and to act as a translator from and to local knowledge.

We have found it useful to join forces with other EU Horizon -funded projects, as well as projects with funding from other (international, national or regional funding). This way the impact of one project can be much larger, than when working alone. Good examples of this work is our joint policy briefs with projects ECOTIP and FACE-IT, concentrating on critical knowledge gaps and research priorities (<https://www.charter-arctic.org/charter-fact-sheets/>). Joint events with Arctic Hubs and JUSTNORTH are other examples. During the very last stages of the project we also established link with Arctic PASSION, and managed to hear their recommendation what comes to working with policymakers.

Discussions in CHARTER final meeting emphasized the importance of genuine and impactful links to decision making. We have done our best to get into dialogue on our research topics, both at EU-level and national/regional level in northern Fennoscandia, and can also show some successes, in this respect. Nevertheless, there is a feeling that more could have been done – and more needs to be done, in future projects. Our colleagues from other Horizon-projects and local collaborators emphasized the importance of “being there” for long enough and building trust, also with policymakers. Local (municipality level) contacts were mentioned. These lessons we will take to our future projects.

In the beginning of the project we started to map our “stakeholders”, and talked about our “target audiences”. During the project we have learnt that the word “stakeholder” should be accompanied by words “knowledge holder” and “right-holder”, as well – and that rather than talking about target audiences, we should be talking about research partners. This language we will take with us to our future projects.

Even though the work presented here is at the moment difficult to link to our earlier work on social networks, with larger datasets it would be possible, and this could lead to more impactful research, and more impactful work in disseminating research findings. We want to encourage other projects to try the same methodology. As a method this is innovative, enabling objective evaluation of how impacts can be maximized in the science-policy interface.

In the original workplan, we considered the possibility to document this work in an open-access peer-reviewed article (for example in the journals ‘Political geography’ or ‘Land degradation and society’) that can provide methodological innovation for other researchers interested in improving their policy impacts. With this limited material, this does not seem useful. Nevertheless, we are planning a joint perspective -article with two other Horizon -funded Arctic projects (ArcticHubs and JUSTNORTH) about lessons learnt. Joint reflection on work done on policymaking, and with decision-makers, will be part of that text.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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APPENDIX

Survey questions and responses. Responses given to open questions in Finnish translated into English.

1. Please consider your participation in CHARTER project activities. Did you feel involved, and that your knowledge was appreciated, when you participated in CHARTER work?

- *I have felt involved. I have experienced that my knowledge and views are valued*
- *Yes*
- *Successful dialogue between research and administration.*
- *Yes*
- *I have felt that my knowledge and views are valued by the project employees. I have felt that I have fully participated in the workshops.*
- *I have felt included and felt that I am valued. The project has always had a positive and respectful undertone.*
- *I have only been involved since 2022 or -23. I started 2022 with the Paliskuntai association. Probably someone else from our organization was more involved in the beginning. I admit that at the beginning I was not fully aware of the scope of the Charter consortium, several research projects are running simultaneously all the time.*
- *The cooperation, at least with me, intensified towards the end of the project, and I can say that I have felt involved and that my views have been valued. On the other hand, since I myself am a researcher by background, it probably makes it easier for me to participate in something like this.*

What we could do better in the future, so that meaningful involvement, balanced co-production of knowledge and inclusion of different knowledge systems (including local and Indigenous knowledge) are ensured?

- *Very often, people who don't attend workshops and events have tacit knowledge. It would be good if researchers could be involved in everyday work and observe the dynamics and interview people who remain in the background.*
- *More stakeholder events, even online, would be appreciated.*
- *Keep up the good work!*
- *When implemented now, it seemed like a working model, at least to me*
- *It would be very fruitful if the Sámi reindeer herders of Norway, Sweden and Finland could talk to each other without the Finns, because I believe that in such a situation, talking would bring a whole new dimension / level.*
- *The project started in a very challenging time, when public events were not possible. Perhaps a larger introductory seminar could be possible in the future.*
- *It is certainly important to participate in such a way that the participants understand their own role. In the collection and use of diverse information (e.g. local, experiential, indigenous peoples) and materials, the researcher must have relevant research and methodological expertise (e.g. anthropology, social and social sciences), respect and sensitivity towards the informants.*

- *In the participation of reindeer herders, the busy times of the reindeer herding year must be taken into account, and it would be good to compensate the work input at least in terms of possible expenses.*
- *There must also be sensitivity regarding what kind of research is needed locally. It is important to be aware that there are many research projects going on all the time, often they are the same people who are put in these to represent their communities (e.g. reindeer herders), in which case the "participation load" may easily accumulate. The methods of data collection should be weighed carefully (e.g. interviews, workshops vs. surveys); these choices affect what kind of material is finally obtained and what kind of information can be interpreted from it.*

Please estimate to what degree you got new information, or gained knowledge and insights about CHARTER main themes, because of CHARTER work (1 = not at all; 5 = plenty; if you cannot say, please leave empty):

Please give one finding or insight that you consider as especially useful:

- *Climate change and the reduction of natural diversity can be seen in the daily life of those who practice natural activities almost every day. I would very much like measures in addition to the already seen and obvious things.*
- *The academic work was well done.*
- *Bringing research authors, work and results closer to decision-makers through dialogue.*
- *Concrete actions are challenging, there is information, but it is difficult to refine it into practice.*
- *well prepared and guided workshops and especially "simulations"*
- *One point was the realization that the Swedish discussion about the effects of reindeer grazing on the diversity of fell areas and e.g. to control global warming (albedo effect), is very different from the Finnish discussion on similar topics. It would be good to think*

- about the reasons for the difference, because I don't think they can be found in nature itself, reindeer numbers, land use and climate or its changes.*
- *Changing summer conditions and thinking about adapting to them along with winter conditions is another.*

To whom have you or might you communicate new knowledge or insights that you have gained over the project lifespan?

- *It is important that basic research is also carried out, which reduces empty questioning and enables the setting of measures and goals. We have used information from e.g. in local development work.*
- *Stakeholders outside the Arctic who are interested in knowing more about the Arctic.*
- *Municipality of Inari*
- *for reindeer herders, reindeer herding cooperatives, reindeer management*
- *For stakeholders, the wider public.*
- *Certainly in every direction that I consider relevant: administration, political actors (at all levels), research community, constituencies, stakeholders*

Do you think this information has been or will be used in planning processes, decision-making, outreach, or in some other way? How?

- *Has come into use in developing the strategy of the Leader group and thus also in local development*
- *It's useful for policymaking on local, national, and even EU level.*
- *As part of continuous evaluation and development.*
- *I believe that good background material can be used for decision-making.. "management with knowledge" in a key position.*
- *especially in his own advocacy work*
- *Not as far as I can see, at least not yet, not really. I hope it will.*

According to your understanding, what limits the use of this information?

- *Inability to apply knowledge, which measures are correct, effective, etc.*
- *Geopolitical tensions*
- *Bureaucracy, money.*
- *the administration's fundamentally negative attitude towards reindeer husbandry, both Finnish and Sami*
- *Certainly at least tenacious attitudes and different political goals for the (land) use of the northern regions.*

CHARTER has had two cross-cutting themes: "Tools and data for Arctic Strategies", and "Public dialogue on the Arctic".

To your knowledge, has CHARTER been able to produce useful data, in a useful form, and useful tools to support future research and decision-making?

- *Not to my knowledge*
- *Yes*
- *Yes*
- *Yes*
- *Researched information related to Arctic nature and land use is always useful*
- *Yes, in a changing environment, producing tools is extremely important.*

- *I would believe that there are, at least things that support future research projects. But in terms of decision-making, it is difficult to judge at this stage.*

In your opinion, has CHARTER been able to actively participate in public dialogue on the Arctic, and/or foster a dialogue in new, meaningful ways?

- *Not that relevant from Sámi perspective*
- *Yes, of course there is always room for improvement, that is, the bearers of tacit information.*
- *It certainly better than if it had not participated in any dialogue at all.*
- *yes, very well*
- *Yes*
- *In my opinion, the focus on reindeer husbandry has been a very important part of the CHARTER project.*
- *The Arctic discussion has almost disappeared from Finland during the last 2.5 years. CHARTER has played a very important role from the point of view of the whole country in keeping Arctic issues in the discussions.*
- *Has participated, but I would like to see more of this participation and continue to do so, even if the project ends. In particular, participation also in non-researcher-to-researcher and internal discussion.*

CHARTER has given some policy recommendations. These are communicated to decision-makers at EU-level, and also at national, regional and local levels. To what degree you agree or disagree on the importance of these (1 = not important at all; 5 = very important; if you cannot say, please leave empty)?

CHARTER has listed some critical knowledge gaps and research needs. To what degree you agree or disagree on the importance of these (1 = not important at all; 5 = very important; if you cannot say, please leave empty):

What other urgent research needs are there, in your opinion?

- *Ecosystem impacts, and links to livelihoods / everyday life of people. Predator-prey interactions, impacts on fish.*
- *More on the changing socioeconomic landscape especially in remote, rural communities.*
- *Inarinjärvi socio-economic survey/research*
- *How could the adaptation of reindeer husbandry to the changing and extreme summer conditions be supported?*
- *How do dry summers affect lichens?*
- *How can reindeer grazing be utilized as part of northern nature care and adaptation to a changing climate, taking into account the practices and culture of reindeer husbandry specific to paliskunta or siida/tokkakunta?*

Other comments?

- *How to take measures from this information. That is the most important question. Everyone is aware that the climate is changing and that there are disadvantages. However, they are not ready to take any measures if it affects economic growth. Among other things, the large impact of tourism on climate change should be recognized and acknowledged by setting restrictions.*
- *A very impressive project.*